

Identification and evaluation of currently available electronic lab notebook solutions for the use within the Berlin University Alliance

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Abstract

The Berlin University Alliance (BUA) is committed to strengthening research data management (RDM) practices in support of Open Science and in alignment with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). As part of the CARDS project (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support), a range of tools and frameworks are being developed to promote resource sharing and foster a collaborative RDM ecosystem across the Alliance's four partner institutions.

Within this context, our sub-project aims to develop a comprehensive strategy for the integration of electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) tailored to the diverse needs of BUA researchers. A key focus lies in conducting detailed needs assessments and evaluating currently available ELN solutions with respect to scalability, cost, interoperability, discipline-specific adaptability, and long-term sustainability. Particular attention is given to the role of open-source ELNs and their community-driven development, which offers flexibility in integrating external devices and customizing workflows across various disciplines.

We also examine critical challenges such as administrative overhead, transferability of data, interoperability of ELN solutions, and the limited adoption of standardized export formats, which influence the long-term viability of ELN implementation. Through this evaluation, we aim to identify ELNs that not only meet current institutional requirements but also support future-proof, FAIR-aligned data practices for a large-scale academic setting.

This paper serves as a transparent record of the criteria, evaluations, and strategic considerations guiding our recommendation for an ELN solution across the BUA. It documents the assessment process that informs the selection of an ELN for the BUA.

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Introduction

In empirical and experimental research, digital recording and annotation of laboratory work are integral to good scientific practice in research data management (RDM). For a long time, research work relied on analogue methods and tools for generating, collecting, and archiving data. In many laboratories, paper lab notebooks (PLNs) were essential for planning, conducting, recording, and documenting experiments. However, the advent of digitization has profoundly transformed research practices. As digital transformation advances, these analogue tools are increasingly being replaced by digital alternatives designed to enhance efficiency, collaboration, security, and the long-term preservation of information and knowledge.

One of the most significant outcomes of this transformation is the way research data is stored and managed. While digital tools offer many advantages, they have also introduced new challenges. The multitude of possibilities has led to data being scattered across multiple locations, including personal computers, local drives, cloud storage, institutional servers, instrument PCs, paper notebooks, and external hard drives. This fragmentation is further compounded by a lack of standardization in file formats, persistent identifiers (PIDs), ontologies, and comprehensive documentation throughout the data lifecycle (Manu & Gala, 2019).

Additionally, documenting data to meet compliance requirements can be labour-intensive and prone to oversights, often omitting critical details. To fully maximize reuse, research data must be well-structured and machine-readable.

This raises the central question of how to identify an ELN that meets BUA-wide requirements while ensuring long-term interoperability and FAIR-aligned data practices.

Electronic laboratory notebooks as a solution

To address these challenges, electronic laboratory notebook (ELNs) have emerged as a digital alternative to PLNs, offering a more structured and efficient approach to data documentation and management. ELNs replace traditional PLNs by providing systems to create, store, retrieve, and share records in compliant ways (Vandendorpe et al., 2024). These tools are known by various names, including electronic laboratory notebooks, digital laboratory notebooks, electronic field notebooks, and electronic engineering logbooks. ELNs not only emulate the core functions of PLNs but also introduce advanced features that enhance data documentation, sharing, and compliance with international policies.

As research environments become increasingly data-driven, demand for institution-wide ELN implementation has grown significantly in recent years. This solution provides a modern, efficient, and secure way to document laboratory activities, enhancing data exchange, accessibility, and security. It enables the standardized recording of experimental details, results, and observations while allowing researchers to share data, collaborate on experiments, and exchange comments in real time. ELNs also automate and streamline the data recording process, providing functions for categorization, tagging, and data storage, improving retrievability and traceability, aligning with FAIR principles.

Another key advantage is that ELNs record user identity, date, and time for each action through authentication and identification, which supports verification processes, such as those related

to patents. The integration of cloud technology further enhances ELN functionality, enabling secure remote access and seamless collaboration among researchers worldwide. Some ELNs also include built-in analysis and visualization tools. Additionally, integrating an ELN with laboratory instruments, when applicable, and other information systems enable the direct transfer of measurement data and metadata, improving research efficiency, data quality, and collaboration among researchers.

Given these advantages, ELNs are increasingly adopted across research and development settings, including industry, academia, and hospitals, to encourage efficient research data management and foster collaboration. For example, ELNs play a crucial role in ensuring Good Research Practice (GRP; Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2025; MRC Working Group, 2012) by enabling transparent tracking and tracing of research workflows. They also support the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) by optimizing the assignment of metadata, tags, and persistent identifiers (PIDs), enhancing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data.

These advantages, along with the growing demand for systematic RDM over the years, led the Berlin University Alliance (BUA)¹ to conclude that a solution should be made available centrally to the partner institutions organised within the BUA.

The project CARDS

The Berlin University Alliance consists of four institutions: Freie Universität Berlin (FU), Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (HU), Technische Universität Berlin (TU), Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin (Charité). It was founded to implement joint projects between these four institutions under one single umbrella organisation. One of the goals of the BUA is to create an IT infrastructure that provides a shared, secure, and controlled environment where data can be collected, processed, analysed, stored, and shared.

Various BUA-funded projects are dedicated to this topic. One of these is the project "Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support" (CARDS, 2024–2026, see Table 1) focusing on the sustainable development and expansion of tools, services and educational offers for research data management (RDM) within the BUA.

Table 1. Subprojects of the BUA-funded project CARDS (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support)

TP1	Implements the open source software "Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)", enhanced with BUA-specific extensions to simplify and improve research data management planning for BUA researchers.
TP2	A Data Steward will implement RDM measures for research groups within clusters of excellence to increase both internal and, when applicable, external data usability
TP3	Expands RDM competency development and training programs to embed RDM expertise within institutions, meet BUA requirements, and establish cooperative connections with other regional and national initiatives.

¹ Berlin University Alliance (2025-12-10). *Homepage of the Berlin University Alliance*. berlin-university-alliance.de <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/>.

TP4 | Identifies the specific requirements and expectations of BUA partners regarding an electronic lab notebook (ELN) solution and develops a concept for introducing an ELN system within BUA.

Here, the fourth sub-project focuses on piloting electronic laboratory notebooks and, based on the experience gained in the piloting phase, is developing an operating and architecture model for an at least one permanent, centralised ELN offering at the BUA in collaboration.

The rationale for this strategic approach arises due to the fact that various research groups and departments at the BUA institutions have already started using ELN applications such as the commercial Labfolder, as well as eLabFTW, Chemotion, NOMAD, Open Enventory and openBIS (all references can be found on Finder²). As there is currently no centrally managed ELN application for BUA institutions, the incompatibility of ELN tools would have hindered collaboration between the universities of excellence and thus efficient RDM, which in turn would have affected the quality and reusability of the collected data.

However, a centralised software solution must be able to strike a balance between the flexibility to cover the workflows of different disciplines and specific functions that meet the requirements of certain academic areas as well as the individual workflows of specific research groups. This is even more essential in a research cluster as large as the BUA with more than 20.000 researchers.

In the following, we evaluate the available ELN tools based on requirements of the BUA partner institutions leading to the selection of a suitable, comprehensive ELN solution by weighing flexibility and scalability against compliance with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Challenges

The selection of an ELN is – among others – based on considerations such as user-friendliness, technical requirements and legal principles (including data protection), which should always be aligned with user needs (ZBMed, 2020) and reviewed in relation to local circumstances (ZBMed, 2020; Dirnagl & Przesdzing, 2016). While the latter aspects are set out in so-called framework service agreements at the institutes (FSA), legal aspects (related to data protection) are regulated in European and national legislation (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR³; Bundesdatenschutzgesetz, BDSG⁴). The legal aspects, in turn, can be further clarified by institutional guidelines, which are often based on FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and open science principles (Vincente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018).

The BUA faces a particular challenge when it comes to the criteria for selecting a specific ELN. Although the GDPR and the BDSG apply equally to all partner institutes, the policies and FSAs of the institutions differ in some respects. Moreover, the Charité is administratively linked to the FU and HU and therefore does not maintain an independent research data policy. However, an IT-specific FSA has been drawn up there, given that patient data is also processed using digital

² TU Darmstadt. (2025-12-10). *ELN Finder Home*. eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de. <https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home>.

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L 119/1

⁴ Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection. (2025-12-10). *Federal Data Protection Act*. gesetz-im-internet.de. https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_bdsge/englisch_bdsge.html.

services in addition to research. In addition, no generally IT-FSA is currently in use at the TU and FU.

In its policy, the FU⁵ provides the most comprehensive information regarding the handling of research data. Requirements for metadata linked to research data are already mentioned here, and the documentation of data generation, processing, indexing and analysis of relevant methods and tools is highlighted as a central point. The latter point is only referred in the HU⁶ policy, while metadata is addressed in the TU policy. However, the TU⁷ has specific recommendations for handling research data in addition, specifying many aspects in a similar way to the FU policy. All policies share a commitment to the FAIR and open science principles.

The IT-FSAs of HU⁸ and Charité⁹ indicate that no service may be misused for behavioural monitoring services must be barrier-free and must enable compliance with user data protection regulations.

Another challenge in selecting an ELN is the number of potential users in the BUA. All four partner institutions employ around 20,000 researchers covering a very broad spectrum of disciplines – with varying requirements in terms of user-friendliness, workflows and specific needs for ELN functions. An ELN to be selected (unless no one is considering an ELN portfolio) must be suitable for the majority of researchers – knowing that it is not possible to cover all needs.

One way to compensate for this gap in coverage is to develop further an ELN independently. This is possible, though, only when the source code of a software is freely available (so-called open-source), which would allow the BUA to develop the specific requirements necessary for its partner institutions itself and make them available to researchers.

Identification of ELNs

To identify an ELNs suitable for the BUA which also meets the principles of Open Science (Vincente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018) and FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), we collected relevant information from multiple sources.

Step 1: Identifying Available ELNs

⁵ Freie Universität Berlin. (2025-12-10). *Team Forschungsdatenmanagement Home*. fu-berlin.de. <https://www.fu-berlin.de/sites/forschungsdatenmanagement/policy/index.html>.

⁶ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. (2025-12-10). *Research data policy of the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*. cms.hu-berlin.de. <https://www.cms.hu-berlin.de/de/dl/dataman/policy>.

⁷ Technische Universität Berlin. (2025-12-10). *Research data policy of the Technical University Berlin*. tu-berlin.de. <https://www.tu.berlin/ueber-die-tu-berlin/organisation/rechtliches/richtlinien-leitlinien/forschungsdaten-policy>.

⁸ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. (2025-12-10). *IT framework service agreement of the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*. gremien.hu-berlin.de. https://gremien.hu-berlin.de/de/amb/2018/111-1/111_2018_it-rahmendienstvereinbarung-der-hu_druck.pdf.

⁹ Charité University Medicine Berlin. (2025-12-10). *IT framework service agreement of the Charité University Medicine Berlin*. klinikpersonalrat.charite.de. https://klinikpersonalrat.charite.de/fileadmin/user_upload/microsites/sonstige/Klinikpersonalrat/Dienstvereinbarungen/20230509_DV_Einf%C3%BChrung_und_Anwendung_von_IT_Systemen_01.pdf.

We began by identifying existing ELNs using the publications by Rubacha et al. (2011) and Higgins et al. (2022), as well as the online resource ELN-Finder¹⁰, hosted by Technische Universität Darmstadt (Technical University Darmstadt). We selected ELN-Finder as the primary reference due to its structured feature catalog, which enables reproducible comparison across tools.

Since Higgins et al. (2022) provide the most up-to-date overview (compared to the somewhat outdated publication by Rubacha et al., 2011), but do not cover all ELNs compared to the ELN-Finder, we conducted our own research to verify the current availability of ELNs to ensure that our information is up to date. For this purpose, we reviewed the internet addresses provided in the sources and/or searched for information using search engines such as Google.

Step 2: Evaluating ELNs for Open Science and FAIR Principles

Given that ELN Finder provides the most detailed information regarding the features of ELNs (compared the other sources), we have used it as a basis for evaluating ELNs in terms of open science and FAIR principles. We gathered information regarding several aspects (software type, payment model, provider location, customization options for user interfaces, integration with secure online services and external devices, compliance with data sovereignty requirements, supported operating systems, and regulatory compliance) and cross-checked through independent research by reviewing the available information on ELNs websites and documentations if available.

Furthermore, we took into consideration that with the growing commitment to open and FAIR data, and given limited financial resources — particularly for scalable solutions — open-source and freely available applications are highly valued at both the university and working group levels. So, we used these two differentiation categories, open-source/proprietary and free/paid, to classify ELNs and to evaluate the different aspects in relation to the needs specified in the chapter above (next chapter).

Evaluation Of Available ELNs

By consolidating data from Rubacha et al. (2011), Higgins et al. (2022), and ELN-Finder¹¹, we identified 92 ELNs currently available on the market. However, Rubacha et al. (2011) and Higgins et al. (2022) do not provide details on the specific features of the ELNs they list. Thus, we focused our further analysis on the 39 ELNs which ELN-Finder lists as currently available and verified systematically the accuracy and relevance of its data.

One of the key questions is the one about specific software licences and payment models as it is likely to be of particular interest to scientific institutions due to financial challenges and the possibility of independently developing these tools in line with individual requirements.

Thirteen of the 39 ELNs are open-source, but only eleven are available completely free of charge. RSpace and SciNote, are only available for a licence fee, even though they are open-source. Please note that even with open source software and freely available software, additional costs may arise, for example for support contracts, operating expenses for implementation and maintenance, and user training, which may also be incurred with paid systems. The remaining 26 ELNs are proprietary, commercially available solutions (see Table 2 for further details).

¹⁰ TU Darmstadt. (2025-12-10). *ELN Finder Home*. eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de. <https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home>.

¹¹ TU Darmstadt. (2025-12-10). *ELN Finder Home*. eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de. <https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home>.

Table 2. Overview of suitable operating systems for ELNs. Note, open-source ELNs in bold font are fee-based. All references can be found on ELN-Finder.

open-source N = 13	AI4Green, Chemotion, eLabFTW, HERBI, Kadi4Mat, Labintegrated Data, NOMAD ELN, OpenInventory, openBIS, PASTA ELN, RSpace , SampleDB, SciNote ,
proprietary N = 26	Agilent SLIMS, Arxspan, Benchling Notebook, BIOVIA Notebook, CDD Vault, Dotmatics Platform ELN, eLabNote, eLabJournal, IDBS e-WorkBook, LabArchives, LabCloud, LabCollector, Labfolder, LabGuru, LABII ELN, Labstep, LabWare, Limsophy, LOGS ELN, Mbook Chemistry, NuGenesis, quattro/LJ, Sapio ELN, SciCord, SciFormation, Uncountable

Since the BUA is a very large science cluster with about 20.000 researchers, the scalability is inherently tied to costs. Even though scalability fundamentally depends on the host's resources, such a potential scale also has corresponding consequences, e.g., increases in administrative support and costs regardless of whether management is handled internally (e.g., across different departments) or outsourced to the provider. It is therefore essential to evaluate whether a self-hosting remains more cost-effective than a user-based licensing scheme, especially since commercial licenses often include support services. Given that most ELNs are proprietary, they run a per-user annual licensing model — ranging from approximately €200 to as much as \$2,400. On the other side, open source does not necessarily mean free of charge: two of the most common open-source ELNs, RSpace and SciNote, even though they are open-source projects, their functional full versions require institutional licenses. However, even if you opt for an ELN without a fee model, there are still administrative costs. Although they offer support for a fee, it is worth calculating precisely whether this is worthwhile and under what conditions it takes place (e.g., can hosting also be provided on your own local servers, or do you have to use the operator's servers).

Open-source ELNs, often free of licensing fees, offer a promising solution to reduce such costs by a significant amount. Yet it should not be forgotten that even free software involves costs such as implementation, administration, training and maintenance. While some of these responsibilities can be outsourced to providers or freelance experts (e.g., through support contracts), they should be factored into institutional workflows and sustainability models, alongside other considerations discussed in detail elsewhere (Dirnagl & Przesdzing, 2016; Higgins et al., 2022; Vandendorpe, 2024).

However, a key advantage of open-source ELNs lies in the strength and engagement of their user communities. By leveraging publicly available source code, these communities actively contribute to further development, particularly in adapting the software to subject-specific needs or integrating external devices and third-party tools. This is particularly advantageous for the BUA, which, unlike a single institution, has to cover the needs of many thousands of researchers and a much wider range of research questions and approaches.

Beyond these rather general issues, however, the BUA still faces very specific challenges. While an institution must consider the needs of their researcher and adhere to its own guidelines when introducing new tools, this is a much greater challenge for a research cluster as large as the Berlin University Alliance. Aspects such as researchers' needs, IT framework service agreements and policies for handling research data must be taken into account not only by one, but by four

institutions. This requires, more than usual, a balance between functionality, flexibility and, above all, compliance with the various guidelines and framework agreements for services.

In addition, many disciplines that do not traditionally rely on lab notebooks must first become familiar with the concept of an ELN. Yet the increasing demands from funding bodies and scientific journals for robust research data management (RDM) plans and strategies for FAIR data practices apply across all fields. In order to match these issues, you need to find an ELN which works for the most of the disciplines and matches the needs of the majority of researchers. Thus, you have to consider when implementing an ELN in a research workflow whether it should be generic or discipline-specific (Vandendorp et al., 2024).

In general, it is difficult to make a clear distinction between so-called generic and discipline-specific ELNs. Many ELNs (e.g., RSpace, Labfolder, eLabFTW) are designed to be easy to use with a simple user interface and adaptable to individual needs, making them accessible to a wide range of disciplines. On the other hand, some ELNs have been developed within specific disciplines (e.g., Chemotion, NOMAD) reflecting the underlying workflows in that field. These ELNs also feature the editors and tools necessary for that discipline to adequately document data (e.g., documenting certain types of data, such as chemical formulas or DNA code snippets). Such aspects are also integrated in some ELNs mentioned at the beginning (e.g., RSpace, eLabFTW, etc.) or are in the planning stage in order to make them usable for specific subject areas. This openness to other disciplines is much more difficult for ELNs developed in a specific environment, even though efforts¹² are being made in this regard. As a rule, so-called generic ELNs are in the majority compared to those developed in a specific discipline environment. Most of the latter are proprietary and require a purchase (e.g., Benchling, eLabNote, LabGuru, Mbook Chemistry), and just a few less are open-source and freely available (e.g., Chemotion, NOMAD, OpenInventory).

In order for the BUA to meet the needs of as many researchers as possible, such specialised ELNs are rather unsuitable unless extensive adjustments are made. This is particularly true since such adjustments based on the needs of researchers can then only be implemented with open source code or by submitting extensive requests to the software operator, who will only consider this from a market economy perspective (or in return for appropriate payment). As a result, it is advantageous for the BUA to rely on generic ELNs since features such as customization and the ability to create reusable templates, offered by most ELNs, serve as low-barrier entry points, making it easier to adopt these tools and meet emerging requirements (Nielsen, 1994).

Yet the choice of a distinct generic ELN for the BUA also depends on other requirements, which may vary from institute to institute. One such requirement is compliance with legal regulations (at regional, national or EU level, i.e. the GDPR). Since the protection of personal data is primarily the responsibility of the users of an ELN, all generic ELNs are basically eligible. It would therefore be more important to clarify which functions the ELNs offer to facilitate the implementation of such requirements, e.g., through comprehensive rights and role management that can be specifically configured at different user levels.

One feature that makes it somewhat easier to implement these requirements is multi-client capability. Multi-client capability refers to the extent to which an instance of an application allows the data of a research group to be viewed by users from other teams within an instance only if the appropriate rights to view and/or modify the data have been assigned. It is about the capability of an application to enable different, separate teams, each of which can make specific adjustments that are only valid for that team, and also to enable communication with external devices and/or software only for that team, without affecting other teams on the same instance.

¹² LabIMotion ELN. (2025-12-10). *LabIMotion Home*. chemotion.net
<https://chemotion.net/docs/labimotion>.

However, it should be noted that the scope of role and rights management varies from ELN to ELN. Some ELNs are designed in such a way (e.g., eLabFTW, openBIS, Labfolder, RSpace) that it eases administration, as only one instance needs to be set up with separated team spaces managed through role-based access control.

The choice in favor of an ELN with multi-client capability, though, may lead to other issues, which has to be taken into account. For example, an instance can only be set up in a specific way, so that certain settings (e.g., templates for data entry or connections to equipment) are effective across all teams. Team-specific customizations and settings (if possible, up to the API level¹³, as enabled by eLabFTW, for example) is therefore another criterion the BUA must consider in order to offer the greatest possible benefit to researchers.

Nevertheless, the multi-client capability enables ELNs to have one advantage over their analogue predecessors: the facilitation of collaboration, both within and across research groups. Although a few tools still have limitations in this area (e.g., LOGS is primarily designed for individual users; HERBI lacks real-time functionality), collaboration features are widely supported across most ELNs, though implemented in varying ways. Version control and even audit trail, on the other hand, is a quite common feature. The same applies to the exchange of data and information, which can be done via local server hosting, as supported by LabFolder, RSpace, eLabFTW, Chemotion, NOMAD and openBIS, for example. On the other hand, all ELNs are subject to the restriction that ELN instances cannot communicate with each other – although a solution is currently being developed. For the BUA, this means that – in order to enable collaboration across the BUA's various locations – only one central instance can be set up, which can be compensated for by means of a potentially existing multi-client capability.

The ELN's data storage location also plays an important role in data security. For the BUA, it is crucial that these comply with the data protection requirements applicable in the EU, which either necessitates the use of a local server or that the relevant servers are located in the EU. However, this aspect may not only be relevant for the BUA in general. Researchers of the BUA also have specific expectations regarding the location of data storage and therefore want to ensure that it is within the network of their host institution, which they consider to be secure. In this regard, the BUA can choose from a couple of ELNs supporting local data storage or even EU-hosted servers (e.g., eLabFTW, SciNote, Labfolder, RSpace).

In addition to these functionalities, the partner institutes of the BUA emphasise accessibility, as it is essential for enabling as many researchers as possible to access the infrastructure. Accessibility is evaluated at the BUA institutions as part of so-called co-determination procedures when introducing new tools^{14,15}, even if some ELNs are already proactively striving to meet the WCAG 2.1 as a standard for accessibility (e.g., eLabFTW, RSpace).

Equally important are user-friendliness and the ability to adapt to the workflow of different working groups or disciplines, since improving the user's workflow is a critical factor for user acceptance, as highlighted in Nielsen's usability heuristics (1994). In this regard, the majority of ELNs listed in ELN-Finder offer easily adaptable interfaces tailored to user requirements. These include flexible text, table, and figure editors, as well as the ability to create custom templates for recurring procedures within a project or across multiple projects. Even if discipline-specific ELNs provide discipline-specific functions, such as editors for chemical formulas and molecular

¹³ Wikipedia. (2025-12-10). *Application Programming Interface*. en.wikipedia.org <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API>.

¹⁴ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. (2025-12-10). *Co-determination procedures at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*. vertretungen.hu-berlin.de. <https://vertretungen.hu-berlin.de/de/gpr/themen/IT-Datenschutz>.

¹⁵ Free University Berlin. (2025-12-10). *Co-determination procedures at Free University Berlin*. fu-berlin.de. <https://www.fu-berlin.de/sites/gpr/it-verfahren/index.html>.

structures, these are increasingly being added to the portfolio of generic ELNs (e.g., RSpace, eLabFTW).

Another feature to improve the workflow is the application programming interface (API) which enables highly customised integration of devices and/or emerging analytical and measurement methods, regardless of discipline. Thus, it brings an invaluable advantage for the BUA in meeting the needs of a wide range of discipline- and researcher-specific workflows and reduces massively the risk of incorrect data entry and thus increases data quality. Moreover, it supports the BUA with the effective use of central infrastructures as many research groups can get access to a larger variety of very expensive equipment across the partner institutions. With the necessary technical expertise within a research institution or working group, adjustments can be implemented relatively easily, provided that the external device itself supports such integration. In this way, an API enables many different working groups from different institutes to access these central elements of scientific work – a feature that, fortunately, many ELNs offer.

In contrast, connectivity to online services such as Figshare or Jupyter is far less common. Among open-source ELNs, only two (RSpace and SciNote, both fee-based) support Figshare, while three (openBIS, eLabFTW, and RSpace) offer integration with Jupyter. Interestingly, among proprietary ELNs, only LabArchives supports both Jupyter and Figshare, whereas Labfolder connects only to Figshare.

As Europe's largest university hospital, Charité Universitätsmedizin is committed to complying with Good Clinical Practice (GCP)¹⁶ standards, which must also apply to an ELN in order to be considered within the BUA. ELNs must guarantee the protection of the identity and integrity of study participants (see above) and enable complete, consistent and structured recording of all study-related activities and observations (a core feature of many ELNs since they provide audit trails and versioning, as in e.g., RSpace, Labfolder, openBIS, eLabFTW etc.). In addition, the application must be validated and regularly audited, something that only a few ELNs can demonstrate (e.g., RSpace, Labii, Labware; evidence based on vendor documentation and published validation reports).

Discussion

Since the release of the first ELN in the early 1980s, the number of available ELNs has grown substantially (Higgins et al., 2022). The earliest ELNs were all commercial products, with the first open-source alternative emerging roughly 15 years later. However, it was not until the technological advances of the 2000s that open-source ELNs began to gain significant traction. As a result, researchers today face an increasingly complex landscape of ELN tools, one marked by rapid changes in availability, licensing models, and feature sets.

In this paper, we presented our identification and evaluation of the electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) currently available on the market listed in the ELN-Finder which are useful for the Berlin University Alliance. The broad range of ELNs reflects the diverse needs of both commercial and academic environments. Scalable from small research teams to large institutions, financial considerations often play a decisive role in determining which ELN is ultimately adopted. Sufficient technical or IT resources as well as the ability to tailor the system to the needs of individual research groups or, at a broader level, to the diverse disciplines and methodologies found across the institutes of the BUA are key factor in the selection process. While subject-

¹⁶ European Medicines Agency. (2025-12-10). *Good clinical practice*. [ema.europa.eu. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/compliance-research-development/good-clinical-practice](https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/compliance-research-development/good-clinical-practice).

specific ELNs can meet the particular demands of certain disciplines, they fall short in serving interdisciplinary environments as it is represented in the BUA. In this context, highly customizable, generic open-source solutions are more suitable.

In addition to continuous development by ELN providers, active user communities play a crucial role in meeting discipline-specific requirements and sharing solutions on open platforms such as GitHub. This is a valuable resource for the BUA, which must actively participate in ensuring the continued growth and availability of these resources. The partner institutes are constantly making new contributions to active research in this area (e.g., in the form of input on workflows, standard operating procedures or the development of new measuring devices), which can be implemented by people with programming skills via API interfaces.

Active participation in the (further) development of applications is closely linked to the question of their continued availability, as it demonstrates ongoing interest in the software and ensures its usability by adapting it to future requirements.

However, this may not always prevent software from being withdrawn from the market or at least no longer supported by the operators (who must further develop the core structure of the software in relation to future technologies). Research institutes must therefore also address the issue of transferring their data to new systems. The introduction of the platform-independent format, initiated by the ELN Consortium¹⁷ and published as open-source code on GitHub, is an important step towards improving interoperability between ELNs. However, its introduction has so far been limited to open-source platforms. In future, the goal (also for the BUA) should be to implement this format as a standardised feature in all ELNs, regardless of their licensing model, in order to ensure long-term data portability and compatibility.

To facilitate the selection of an ELN for the BUA, the ELN Finder of the Technical University of Darmstadt was consulted, but it still lists 39 available ELNs. In this context, it is helpful to know which ELNs are centrally managed at which German research institutes, for example to facilitate collaboration. The NFDI4Chem guidance indicates that eLabFTW (N = 19) and Chemotion (N = 22) are by far the most widely used, followed by RSpace and Labfolder (N = 3 each).

However, since ELNs (as in the present article) are often selected based on local aspects, a list of potentially suitable ELNs should cover a wider range to ensure that the relevant needs of the BUA are not overlooked. An LLM query listed the following ELNs in addition to those just mentioned: LabArchives, LOGS, Benchling, LabCollector, Labii ELN & LIMS, SciNote, Kadi4Mat, Pasta-ELN, Herbi, NOMAD, openBIS and Open Enventory (all references can be found on ELN-Finder).

The information gathered from the ELN Finder (see supplement) regarding these ELNs forms the basis for the BUA's evaluation and selection of an ELN after its validity had been checked (comparison of the information with the provider's website and the community pages on Git). Based on the criteria and institutional requirements, openBIS and eLabFTW currently offer the most viable balance of scalability, adaptability, and FAIR-aligned sustainability for the BUA.

Our evaluation reflects the state of ELN availability and documentation at the time of analysis and may shift as software ecosystems evolve.

Acknowledgements

¹⁷ ELN Consortium (2025-12-10). *Github-page of the ELN Consortium*. github.com/theelnconsortium

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Supplement

Supplemental table s1. Overview on the features of the most commonly used ELNs on the market.

ELN Name	Software license	Payment model (contact the provider for license fees or for academic licence options)	Service Costs
Labfolder	proprietary	user/year	with additional costs: on-Premise-installation, private cloud-solution, personalized onboarding
LabArchives	proprietary	user/year	Professional plan: NIH Data Management Mandates & Sharing support
LOGS	proprietary	no data available	no data available
Benchling	proprietary	user/year	no data available
LabCollector	proprietary	user/year	included in the license
Labii ELN	proprietary	user/year	included in the license
SciNote	proprietary	user/year	included in the license
RSpace	open-source	user/year	included in the license
eLabFTW	open-source	free	Fee-based: email support, virtual meeting support, level 2 & 3 support, 2-hour user training webinar
Chemotion	open-source	free	support by helpdesk available
Kadi4Mat	open-source	free	support by helpdesk available
PASTA-ELN	open-source	free	support by helpdesk available
HERBIE	open-source	free	support by community only
NOMAD	open-source	free	support by community and helpdesk
openBIS	open-source	free	support by community and helpdesk
Open Enventory	open-source	free	no data available

Note. This overview is based on a request about the most common ELNs for academia and on entries at inder.net. The information was subsequently verified, supplemented, or corrected through our own research. Any information labeled as unverified refers to details that could not be confirmed through independent verification.

ELN Name	Support and Training
Labfolder	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Community, Webinar
LabArchives	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Webinar
LOGS	no data available
Benchling	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Resources, fee-based trainings available, Community
LabCollector	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, fee-based trainings available, ticket system, custom training
Labii ELN	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Trainings, Tickets, fee-based trainings available
SciNote	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Webinars, Community,
RSpace	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Community
eLabFTW	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, fee-based trainings available, Community
Chemotion	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, optional workshops
Kadi4Mat	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials
PASTA-ELN	Community
HERBIE	Demo, Documentation, Community (Open Science), Multiple support options including paid and free
NOMAD	Webinar
openBIS	Demo, Documentation, Tutorials, Community, Trainings
Open Enventory	no data available

ELN Name	Compliance	Security
Labfolder	HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, ISO 27001, AES-256, HTTPS/SSL, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
LabArchives	HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, ISO 27001, AES-256, HTTPS/SSL, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
LOGS	no data available	SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
Benchling	GDPR, HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, AES-256, HTTPS/SSL, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
LabCollector	HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, AES-256, HTTPS/SSL, SAML/LDAP, MFA/2FA, etc
Labii ELN	GDPR, HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, AES-256, HTTPS, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
SciNote	GDPR	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, HTTPS, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
RSpace	GDPR, HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SOC2, ISO 27001, AES-256, HTTPS/SSL, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
eLabFTW	GDPR, HIPAA	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, HTTPS/SSL, SAML/LAPD, MFA/2FA, etc
Chemotion	GDPR	HTTPS, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
Kadi4Mat	GDPR	HTTPS, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
PASTA-ELN	GDPR	no data available
HERBI	GDPR, DDP, and NESA	ISO 27001:2022, HTTPS, SAML, MFA/2FA, etc
NOMAD	no data available	HTTPS, SSO, MFA/2FA, etc
openBIS	GDPR	FDA CFR 21 Part 11, SAML/LAPD, MFA/2FA, etc
Open Enventory	no data available	HTTPS/SSL, MFA/2FA, etc

2FA, two-factor authentication; AES, Advanced Encryption Standard; CFR, Code of Federal Regulations; FDA, Food and Drug Administration; LDAP, Lightweight Directory Access Protocol; MFA, multi-factor-authentication; SAML, Security Assertion Markup Language; SOC, Service Organization Control.

ELN Name	Data Export	Backup Options
Labfolder	PDF, XHTML, JSON, etc.	cloud, local server, data export
LabArchives	PDF, HTML, XML, CSV, XLSX, etc.	cloud, data export, bi-hourly, encrypted backups
LOGS	no data available	no data available
Benchling	PDF, HTML, DOCX, CSV, XLSX, PZFX, etc.	no data available
LabCollector	PDF, HTML, XML, CSV, XLSX, etc.	local server, data export, database
Labii ELN	TSV, XLSX, etc.	API, cloud, data export
SciNote	PDF, HTML, CSV, XLSX, ELN, etc.	s3 compatible storage, database, data export
RSpace	PDF, HTML, XML, DOC, etc.	s3 compatible storage, local server, database, data export
eLabFTW	PDF, HTML, XML, CSV, JSON, ELN, etc.	s3 compatible storage, local server, full virtual machine backup, manual/automated backups
Chemotion	HTML, DOCX, ODT, CSV, XLSX, ZIP, etc.	cloud, local server
Kadi4Mat	ELN, RDF, etc.	s3 compatible storage, local server, data export,
PASTA-ELN	ELN, etc.	local server, database, data export, repositories
HERBI	no data available	cloud, local server, data exports
NOMAD	JSON, ELN (import only), ZIP, etc.	cloud, local server, database, data export
openBIS	PDF, TSV, XLSX, JSON, ZIP, etc.	cloud, local server, database
Open Enventory	PDF, CSV, XLSX, XLS, SDF, etc.	no data available

ELN Name	Collaboration and Sharing	Integration with Other Software
Labfolder	supports collaboration, sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Supports API integration with common platforms
LabArchives	supports collaboration, sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Supports integration with external apps and databases
LOGS	basic collaboration options (primarily for individuals), sharing possible, version control	Supports integration, requires custom configuration
Benchling	supports collaboration (especially for team-based research), sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Multiple integrations with other lab software and databases
LabCollector	supports collaboration (primarily for individuals), sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Basic integrations, mostly with own ecosystem
Labii ELN	supports collaboration, cloud sharing, version control, audit trail	Integration with popular LIMS systems, external apps
SciNote	supports collaboration, cloud sharing, version control, audit trail	Integration with external platforms supported
RSpace	supports collaboration (also options via cloud), sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code, mostly with native tools
eLabFTW	supports collaboration (cloud and server-based), sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code
Chemotion	supports collaboration (cloud and server-based), sharing possible, version control, audit trail	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code
Kadi4Mat	supports collaboration, sharing possible	Few integrations, mostly internal tools
PASTA-ELN	supports collaboration (cloud and server-based), sharing possible	Easy integration with cloud services, Wide range of integrations with data systems

HERBI	supports collaboration (but lacks real-time features), mainly cloud sharing	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code
NOMAD	supports collaboration, sharing possible, version control	Limited third-party integrations
openBIS	lacks collaboration tools for research teams, version control, audit trail	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code
Open Enventory	supports collaboration, basic sharing features (useful for teams), version control	Supports integration with external tools due to open source code

ELN Name	Customization and Usability
Labfolder	highly customizable, advanced setup required
LabArchives	limited customization options, user-friendly,
LOGS	highly customizable, interface is a bit dated
Benchling	customizable for molecular biology, user-friendly
LabCollector	some level of customization, outdated interface
Labii ELN	customizable fields and templates, intuitive interface
SciNote	customizable workflows, easy to use
RSpace	multiple customization options and templates, intuitive
eLabFTW	highly customizable, requires technical setup
Chemotion	customizable workflows, highly user-friendly
Kadi4Mat	customizable templates
PASTA-ELN	custom workflows and templates, good usability
HERBI	customization requires programming, intuitive
NOMAD	limited customization, easy-to-use
openBIS	hard to customize, intuitive
Open Enventory	moderate flexibility